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Coastal flooding and erosion at Dniester's barrier beach (Ukraine)

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Coastal flooding and erosion at Dniester's barrier beach (Ukraine)

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Final degree project supervised by Dr. Vicente Gracia and professor Joan Pau Sierra

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ABSTRACT

The barrier beach of the Dniester river (Ukraine) has a length of about 10 km and a width of 100 m at its narrowest point. Its height varies from about +3m up to more than +5m in the wider zone. The original natural foredune has been almost completely removed and, at present, the barrier is completely occupied by a road, a railway, houses and touristic resorts. Due to its low-lying nature, the area is considered a highly sensitive coast of the Black Sea (Tătuț et al.; 2019) and such characteristics will be intensified in the future due to sea level rise and extreme events induced by climate change.

The aim of this study is to determine the vulnerability of Dniester barrier beach to wave storms through the use of the morphodynamic numerical model XBeach.

Three main elements have been considered for the study: the digital elevation model, the morphological characteristics and the hydrodynamic conditions. First, the topography and bathymetry of the Dniester area have been combined into a variable rectangular grid, with a resolution of up to 50 m in the open sea and 2-5 m in the area of interest. Second, Odessa State Environmental University (OSENU) collected sediment samples from three beaches located in the north, center, and south of the barrier, and a particle size distribution was obtained by sieve analysis. And third, a study of the extreme wave climate was performed using the ERA5 dataset and the Gumbel probability distribution function was adjusted using the Annual Method Maximum (AMM). The associated return periods have been calculated, with a maximum of 43 years for a given significant wave value of more than 5 m. This analysis has been used to assess the response in terms of beach flooding and erosion to events with different Middle Sea Level (NMM) scenarios.

In October 2016, the media reported an episode of coastal flooding on the south of the barrier that caused severe damage to coastal infrastructure. This event has been used to qualitatively validate the XBeach model.

The results obtained have shown three main areas where floods have the greatest impact. In addition, it has been observed that erosion has been predominant along the barrier beach coast, while sedimentation processes have been focused at the inlet, a key point of connection between the estuary and the sea. In all cases, NMM has been shown to be a determining factor in the magnitude of the effects, both in terms of flooding and erosion / sedimentation. These results can be very useful for future barrier management.

Key words: Barrier beach, Coastal flooding, XBeach, Erosion, Modelling, Extreme Value Analysis.

RESUM

La platja de barrera del riu Dnièster (Ucraïna) té una longitud d'uns 10 km i una amplada de 100 m en el seu punt més estret. La seva alçada varia des d'uns +3m fins a més de +5m a la zona més ampla. El sistema dunar natural original ha estat gairebé eliminat i, actualment, la barrera està totalment ocupada per una carretera, un ferrocarril, cases i centres turístics. A causa de la seva naturalesa baixa, la zona es considera una costa altament sensible del mar Negre (Tătui et al.; 2019) i aquestes característiques s'intensificaran en el futur a causa de l'augment del nivell del mar i els esdeveniments extrems induïts pel canvi climàtic.

L'objectiu d'aquest estudi és determinar la vulnerabilitat de la platja barrera de Dniester (Odesa, Ucraïna) davant de temporals fent servir el model morfodinàmic XBeach.

S'han considerat tres elements principals per fer l'estudi: el model digital d'elevació, les característiques morfològiques i les condicions hidrodinàmiques. En primer lloc, la topografia i la batimetria de la zona de Dniester s'han combinat en una malla rectangular variable, amb una resolució de fins a 50 m a mar obert i 2-5 m a la zona d'interès. En segon lloc, la OSENU (Odessa State Environmental University) va recollir mostres de sediments de tres platges situades al nord, al centre i al sud de la barrera, i es va obtenir una distribució granulomètrica mitjançant l'anàlisi de tamisatge. Finalment, s'ha realitzat un estudi del clima d'onatge extremal utilitzant el conjunt de dades de ERA5 i s'ha ajustat la funció de distribució de probabilitat de Gumbel mitjançant el Mètode Màxims Anuals (AMM). S'han calculat els períodes de retorn associats, sent el màxim 43 anys per un valor d'altura significant d'onada de més de 5 m. Aquest anàlisi s'ha utilitzat per avaluar la resposta en termes d'inundació i erosió de la platja davant d'esdeveniments amb diferents escenaris del Nivell Mig del Mar (NMM).

L'octubre de 2016, els mitjans de comunicació van informar d'un episodi d'inundació costanera al sud de la barrera que va causar greus danys a les infraestructures costaneres. Aquest esdeveniment s'ha utilitzat per validar qualitativament el model XBeach.

Els resultats obtinguts han revelat tres àrees principals on les inundacions tenen majors afectacions. A més, s'ha pogut observar com l'erosió ha sigut majoritària al llarg de la costa de la platja barrera, mentre que els processos de sedimentació s'han focalitzat a l'entrada, un punt clau de connexió entre l'estuari i el mar. En tots els casos s'ha vist com el NMM és factor determinant en la magnitud de les afectacions, tan en termes d'inundació com en erosió/sedimentació. Aquests resultats poden ser de gran utilitat per a la futura gestió de la barrera.

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1. Introduction: Motivation and objectives

This work is part of DOORS (Developing Optimal and Open Research Support for the Black Sea), an EU research project that aims to connect science, industry and citizens to regenerate the Black Sea and advance a blue economy horizon involving a total of 37 institutions.

The north-western part of the Black Sea is a very large continental shelf area where deltaic ecosystems, estuaries and barrier beaches are predominant. The extreme events such as storms surges can have a great impact on these areas due to their low laying nature.

In the current context of climate emergency, it is essential to advance our knowledge for future catastrophic events in order to implement preventive methods. We are also experiencing an unprecedented demographic increase, and coastal areas are precisely the most populated areas. Sea level rise and shoreline regression are already happening in many areas of the planet, and that is why interdisciplinary management across all sectors is required to achieve the least possible impact, especially on less resilient populations. A specific case in this multidisciplinary task facing society today is the coastal management, where morphodynamic models can be of great help in understanding and predicting the expected morphological changes of shorelines.

The main objective of this work is to determine the vulnerability in terms of flooding and erosion of the Dniester barrier beach located in Odesa (Ukraine) in front of extreme wave events using the XBeach morphodynamic model. In addition, emphasis has been placed on characterising the waves by applying the Extreme Value Analysis (EVA), thus estimating the return periods.

The work is divided into three main blocks: in the first, a digital elevation model has been constructed using the topo-bathymetry of the study area as a reference, in the second, a granulometric curve has been created based on the sieving study provided by Odessa State Environmental University (OSENU), while in the third block, the extreme wave regime and the response of the barrier beach in front of extreme events were studied.

2. Study area

2.1 General context and morphology

The Dniester beach (Ukraine) is a narrow low-lying sandy barrier located at the end of the Dniester River, one of the most important transboundary rivers in Eastern Europe. The river rises at the Ukrainian Carpathians, flows through the Republic of Moldova and finally ends in the Dniester estuary, at Ukraine, which is defended from the Black Sea through the barrier (Figure 2.1, upper panel). The Dniester overall length is about 1.350 km and has a drainage basin of about 72.000 km² being the mean water discharge of about 310 m³/s (Denisov et al., 2016). The estuary, very shallow, has a maximum depth of less than 3 m and it has a total surface of about 408 km².

The original natural foredune (Figure 2.1, lower panel), which can still be observed at some areas from the satellite images and photos taken by visitors, has been almost completely removed. At present, the barrier is fully occupied by buildings, seafront promenades, a railway and a road with a bridge at the Dniester inlet used as the main route to connect the northern Ukrainian coastal cities with the southern Black Sea neighbouring countries. Before the 2022 war, the barrier was a very popular touristic destination due to, among other things, its proximity to the city of Odessa located 45 km at the north supporting many tourist resorts build very close to the shoreline and less than 5 m in the worst case.

The low-lying nature of the barrier makes it highly vulnerable to extreme events in which the infrastructures are totally exposed (Tătui et al.; 2019). Similar situations are seen on many other coasts, where most of the constructions were built underestimating the dynamism of the beaches (FitzGerald et al., 2008). Besides, this situation of high exposure and low resilience is expected to increase in future due to the sea level rise induced by climate change and, as a consequence, the vulnerability to flooding from extreme events such as storms waves acting simultaneously with high tides as reported by Griggs & Reguero, (2021) is expected to be higher.

The coastal landscape of the area is dominated by lagoons, wetlands and barriers that extend for more than 750 km, many of them declared as Ramsar sites of international significance. The continental shelf extends for more than 150 km, the widest in the Black Sea. The isobaths -100 m marks the end of the shelf and the start of the continental slope. The lobular shape of the -20 m depth contour can be associated to relict deltas (Figure 2.2) and have an influence, due to refraction, on wave incidence at the coast. The coastal slope, understood as the slope between the shoreline and the isobath 20 m is gentle and varies between 0.25° and 0.6°. These values have been associated to areas least sensitive to coastal erosion by Tătui et al. (2019). The same authors analysed the shoreline evolution from a set of satellite images covering 33 years (from 1984 to 2017) and determine that the coastal stretch of Dniester can be considered as stable with shoreline trends between -1 m/year to +1 m/year. However, they also found a strong correlation between high erosion rates and coastal barriers situated in the north western side of the Black Sea basin. They conclude that the Dniester coast is a highly sensitive area due to its low-lying nature and the degree of exposure to waves and surges.

Figure 2.1: Dniester barrier beach location. Upper panel: A) Global view of southern Europe. B) Zoom in on the north-western part of the Black Sea. C) Barrier beach location at the Dniester estuary. Lower panel: photos of the barrier beach taken by different Google users.

The length of the barrier is about 10 km and it has an average width of 550 m being the narrowest section of about 100 m at the north, near to Solnechnoe (Figure 2.1.C, upper panel). An inlet of 225 m wide at the centre south of the barrier connects the estuary with the Black Sea and is used as the maritime entrance by the port facilities located inside the estuary. The height of the barrier varies from +3 m up to more than +5 m in the highest zone being the total emerged area of about 7 km².

Figure 2.2: Screen capture from bathymetric chart taken from Navionics. The black line represents the -20 m isobath.

2.2 Hydrodynamic Forcing

2.2.1 Sea Currents

The general circulation pattern of the Black Sea (Figure 2.3) is a wind-driven current known as the Rim current. The Rim current runs around the steep continental slope and separates the coastal circulation patterns with the deep sea. There are two smaller cyclonic gyres in the eastern and western sectors of the basin. They are well-formed systems in winter (start in spring) but dissipate into little interconnected eddies in summer and autumn (Korotaev et al., 2003). This is useful to understand the hydrodynamic conditions and the spatial distribution of the extreme events although generally, southern coast of the Crimea Peninsula, the southwestern and the north-eastern part of the sea are the most affected by storms and extreme weather conditions (Divinsky et al., 2020).

Figure 2.3: Black Sea main circulation patterns (Kershaw, 2015).

There is not a clear cyclic circulation in the study area, since cyclonic and anticyclonic eddies occupy much of the open Black Sea but few are found on the north-western shelf (Sadighrad et al., 2021). Combination of local winds and wave forcing dominates the dynamics of the study region. Additionally, the wave events are not as energetic as in other locations, even so, they can cause significant damages and changes to the landscape due to the sandy composition of the beaches and their gentle profiles.

2.2.2 Wave heights of combined wind waves and swell

The enclosed nature of the Black sea may lead to think that waves will not be as powerful as in open oceans in terms of wave height due to the difference of fetch (i.e. the length of water over wind blows without obstruction). While wind wave is related to the local wind, swell is limited by the geographic characteristics of the basin. Even though, many extreme events with waves heights similar to those that would occur in the open oceans has been reported (Rusu 2016; Divinsky et al., 2020). There have even been registered cases of Freak waves (Divinsky et al., 2004).

According to Tătui et al., (2019), the significant wave height on the Black Sea ranges from 0.85 to 1.84 meters when reaching the coast. Focusing on the study region, the mean significant wave heights vary between 0.85 m and 0.97 m. In general, the southwestern part has a steeper slope and waves are more energetic, meanwhile the north-western part is characterised by much gentler slopes and more moderate waves; therefore the maximal significant wave height decrease around the shallow north-western coasts (Gippius & Myslenkov, 2020).

Extreme events are mainly differentiated into three major regions: in the south-western part of the sea they occur in January and December, on the southern coast of the Crimea peninsula they occur in February, and in the north-eastern part of the sea they appear in November (Divinsky et al., 2020).

2.2.3 Effective wave incidence

Tatui et al., (2019) determine the potential impact of waves on the coast through the wave incidence angle, that is, the angle between the shoreline and the incident waves in such a way that the closer to 90° (perpendicular to shore), the higher the potential impact. Their results show that the incidence angle distribution is highly variable along the coasts of the Black Sea and it is difficult to establish regional patterns. Even so, the wave incidence in the study region is predominantly between 54° and 72°, which means that there is a dominant transverse dynamic with some longitudinal component.

Taking into consideration those ranges of incidence and the orientation of Dniester barrier beach, the effective wave incidence in this particular case goes from 40° to 220°, respect to the north (Figure 2.4).

Figure 2.4: Effective Significant Wave Incidence in the Dniester barrier beach.

2.2.3 Tides

Tides can be generically represented as the sum of two types of water motions: co-oscillation tides, which are caused by the tidal oscillation of an adjacent basin, and the independent tides, which are caused directly by the influence of the tide-generating forces of the Moon and the Sun. In the enclosed seas independent tides strongly prevails in front of co-oscillation tides, which are almost negligible (Defant, 1961).

The Black Sea has close connections with the Mediterranean Sea and The Atlantic Ocean through Bosphorus, Dardanelles and Strait of Gibraltar, and it does not perceive much influence from neighbouring tides (Medvedev et al., 2016). A study by Medvedev (2018) in which 28 tide gauges were examined found that the semidiurnal tides prevail over diurnal tides, specifically in the north-western part. The results indicate that semidiurnal tides prevail on the east and west, while in the central part of the sea both types were approximately equal.

The Black Sea coasts present a micro-tidal regime (Korotaec et al., 2001), with maximum micro-tidal range varying from 1.1 cm near the Crimean Peninsula to 19 cm in the Dnieper–Bug Estuary, up to 12.6 cm in Batumi and 13–14 cm at Odesa, near the studied region.

2.2.4 Sea Level Rise

Since the Black Sea is a practically closed sea of small dimensions, nowadays sea level rise (SLR) represents a rather low risk for the moment, although in the upcoming decades it could become a major problem (Güneroğlu et al., 2019). Instead, the highest RSLR (Relative Sea Level Rise) rates are encountered especially on the north-western part of the basin, reaching 3mm/year, and in large areas in the north (Crimea), north-eastern (in front of the Great Caucasus Mts.) and east (on the Georgian coast) (Tătui et al., 2019).

A recent work published by Avşar and Kutoğlu (2020) has studied sea level change in coastal and open sea areas with the temporal data of 12 tide gauges and satellite altimetry, concluding a generalize increase in both areas and confirming that seasonal sea level variations in the Black Sea reach their maximum annual amplitude in May–June.

Most of the coastline is potentially vulnerable to erosion processes, especially in the deltaic and estuarine areas. Coastal territories in the South of Ukraine will suffer intensive impacts from SLR. Crimea Peninsula, the Kherson Region and the Odesa Region (specially the Danube Delta) will be affected the most (Holubstov et al., 2018).

The results of Avsar and Kutoglu (2019) conclude that modelling sea level changes as a function of time and space is crucial for assessing the resulting risk and planning the use of coastal areas. Local, regional and national patterns need to be considered to identify coastal vulnerabilities and the future effects of SLR.

In the global context, storms and extreme events will have greater impacts, leading to higher rates of coastal erosion (Morim et al., 2021). Then, the coastal management will be a priority in the near future.

3. Data and Methods

The coastal flooding and erosion assessment at Dniester barrier beach have been done through the use of the open source numerical model XBEACH. A review of storm impacts in the area has permitted identify a storm causing severe overwash and damages on infrastructures. This event has been used to qualitatively validate the model. Afterwards, the same storm event has been simulated with a mean water level rise of 0.7 m. Such new condition is representative of a plausible future climate change scenario. The results of this second simulation has been used to determine the vulnerability of the coast against flooding and erosion for the same storm conditions.

A workflow diagram is presented in Figure 3.1 to schematically represent the steps followed during this work. The tasks performed to run the model have been grouped in three main categories: (i) Topo-bathymetry definition, (ii) Morphology characterisation and (iii) Hydrodynamic conditions. Additionally, an analysis of extreme values (EVA) has been performed to statistically characterise the event. In the first section, the objective has been to create a digital elevation model (DEM), in the second one, the grain size distribution has been obtained (D50), and in the third one, the storm of October 2016 has been characterised and the extreme wave regime has been evaluated.

The topo-bathymetry, morphology and hydrodynamics conditions are used to construct the numerical model of Dniester barrier beach. The XBeach model is used, giving as a result the coastal flooding and erosion over the grid in time. Finally, a post-process of the results has been done to graphically represent the above-mentioned hazards.

The following sections explain in detail the methodology used in each task.

Figure 3.1: Workflow diagram of the study.

3.1 Digital Elevation Model (DEM)

The DEM has been built from two different sources of data available on the web: (i) the bathymetric data taken from EMODnet (European Marine Observation and Data Network) and (ii) the topographic information taken from NASADEM Global Digital Elevation Model. It has to be pointed out that the use of different sources of spatial information, especially in this area, makes the DEM difficult to be exported into a universal reference system because the detailed information of coordinate system used in each is many times missed or hard to find. However, I have prioritized the NASADEM data set because it provides the most detailed information of the emerged part of the barrier. The resulting grid has several mismatches with the images provided by GoogleEarth and forces to treat the results as graphs rather than using a GIS platform.

Regarding EMODnet (European Marine Observation and Data Network), after selecting the area of interest through its portal, I have taken the RGB format where each colour tone in the greyscale is associated to one depth because it allows us to directly incorporate the file in the other software. The topography data extracted from the NASADEM Global Digital Elevation Model with an ASCII format because the zone of the barrier beach has low-resolution on the EMODnet data.

Once the bathymetry and topography has been downloaded, a grid was constructed with the combination of both files using the *'set group layers'* function of the Global Mapper software. Minimum and maximum depth values have been specified for each file, ensuring that the bathymetry includes the negative values (corresponding to the water area) while the topography includes the positive (land area).

Once both files have been combined, the new file is exported in ASCII format with a sample spacing of 2m to improve and smooth the topo-bathymetry with the software Surfer. It is also exported in kmz format and transformed into geographical projection in order to visualize the elevations in Google Earth, see Figure 3.2 for visual inspection.

Figure 3.2: Topo-bathymetry of the study case in Odesa region visualized through Google Earth.

It has been assumed that the coastline shows a uniform distribution along the beach for the subsequent modelling, that is why it has been smoothed the 0 m coastline using the 'pull up' tool of Surfer® and having as reference the nautical chart provided by Odessa State Environmental University (OSENU), see ANNEX A.

The most precise improvements have been made to the coastline on the south side (coastline sea front) and at the inlet of the barrier beach. Other modifications such as setting the estuary depth to -1.5m have also been done. See Figure 3.3 for a comparison between the original file and the smoothed version.

Figure 3.3: Grid resolution comparison of the Dniester barrier beach. a) Combined EMODnet and NASADEM file imported into Surfer without modifications. b) Smoothed version of combined EMODnet and NASADEM file in Surfer.

Then, the improved grid is exported to ASCII format and introduced to the Delft Dashboard software in WGS 84 UTM zone 36N that will allow working with XBeach. This program is a standalone application build on MATLAB by Deltares and allows to generate a variable grid, which means that the variation of one or both axes is different through the grid. In our case, we need the highest resolution on the area of interest (the barrier beach) so our dx vary from 30m offshore to 2m in the land (Figure 3.4).

Figure 3.4: Variation grid resolution (*marks the offshore boundary and ** the zone of interest corresponding to the barrier beach).

This configuration has been selected because the interest is in obtaining results along the entire beach. If the dy were also variable, then there would be areas parallel to the shore where it would not have adequate resolution to study the entire coastline. This configuration allows optimising the computational cost when performing the simulations. See Figure 3.5 for a visual simplification of the mesh.

Figure 3.5: Simplification of the variable grid of the Dniester barrier beach using Delft Dashboard.

Having specified the values of the spacing between nodes and the selected area, the next step is to generate the DEM (Figure 3.6), resulting as outputs the needed files to run XBeach model, explained in detail in Section 3.4).

Figure 3.6: Digital Elevation Model (DEM) generated through Delft Dashboard.

3.2 Extreme Wave Regime

Coastal flooding and erosion are typically associated to extreme events, a sea state in which a specified threshold of wave height is exceeded. The statistical characterisation of waves is a fundamental tool in any coastal study because it allows to assess the probability of occurrence of extreme sea states through the definition of the best probability distribution function of extreme values of the wave height. The extreme wave climate analysis has as a main result the characterisation of the return period, also known as a recurrence interval, the average time in years between extreme events to occur.

In this work, *Pyextremes* Python library from Bocharov (2021) has been used for the Extreme Value Analysis (EVA). It is a statistical discipline focused on the stochastic behaviour of a given process with atypically high or low values, focusing attention on events associated with distribution queues. The main goal of EVA is to estimate the probability distribution of the extreme values of a variable from a record of empirical samples (Goda, 1988; Coles, 2001). In this case, the aim is to use EVA in order to understand the extreme wave conditions and estimate the return periods of the storms close to the Dniester barrier beach. The freely available ERA5 wave data set is used in the analysis. The ERA5 is a global atmospheric reanalysis product created by the European Centre for Medium-Range Weather Forecast (ECMWF) that provides hourly information on wave parameters from 1979 to present. The variables used in this study have been: (i) the Significant height of combined wind waves and swell, (ii) the Mean wave period and (iii) the Mean wave direction. Additionally, the wave energy flux has been parametrised as the square of the wave height multiplied by wave period to determine the power of waves to transport sediment. Therefore, there are 43 years of hourly data for each variable mentioned above (Figure 3.7).

Figure 3.7: ERA5 time series data for the study area. a) Significant height of combined wind wave and swell. b) Mean wave period. c) Wave Energy. d) Histogram of Mean Wave Direction.

Figure 3.8 shows the available nodes of the ERA5 data set in front of the Dniester coast. A selection criterion of having at least two nodes before reaching the coast is applied. This condition is imposed to avoid any possible landward boundary influence on the data. The selected node is located at 45.4°N 31.14°E .

Figure 3.8: Region of ERA 5 database nodes. In red, the selected node for the study (45.4°N , 31.14°E).

The EVA has been done considering the effective directions, that is, the sea states that reached the coast. The objective is to determine the probability of non-exceedance of those extremes conditions that can cause an impact on the barrier rather than considering all possible wave directions. Thus, a subset of data have been extracted from the entire data within the 45° - 215° considering the coastline orientation and leaving a 5° safety margin (see Figure 4.1 in section 4.1).

With this new data set, the wave height design values (which are the extreme values selected for the further analysis) should be determined. There are three general approaches to EVA: The Initial Distribution Method (IDM; Goda, 1988), the Annual Maximum Method (AMM; Coles, 2001), and the Peak Over Threshold Method (POT; Ferreira and Soares, 1998). Nowadays, the common approaches are AMM and POT. In these cases, the aim is to fit an analytical extreme value probability distribution to the data and extrapolate to the desired probability level (Coles et al., 2001). The use of the POT necessary requires the definition of the threshold of an extreme to be considered. However, such information is missed in the area, and because of this, the AMM method has been used.

In the case of the AMM, also called Block Maxima (BM), the maximum value of a time series variable during a period is selected. In order to have a good performance of the method, it is necessary to assume that the events (in our case the storms) correspond to a sample of independent and identically distributed random variables (Caires, 2011). Thus, we select as block size one year, so there is only one extreme event each year of data (see Figure 4.2 in section 4.1).

The next step is to select a model and fitting it to the extracted extreme events. The idea is to find the model parameters that maximize the likelihood metric and give us the best fit possible by the Maximum Likelihood Estimated (MLE) model. This maximum data follows a generalized extreme value distribution (GEVD) where Gumbel, Fréchet and Weibull families (type I, II and III respectively) can be combined into a single family of models having the following distribution function (Castillo and Sarabia, 1988; Coles, 2001):

$$G(z) = \exp \left\{ - \left[1 + \xi \left(\frac{(z - \mu)}{\sigma} \right) \right]^{-\frac{1}{\xi}} \right\}, \quad \begin{array}{l} z \in [\mu - \sigma/\xi, +\infty) \text{ when } \xi > 0, \\ z \in (-\infty, +\infty) \text{ when } \xi = 0, \\ z \in (-\infty, \mu - \sigma/\xi] \text{ when } \xi < 0 \end{array} \quad (1)$$

where z is maximum wave extracted values, μ is a location parameter, σ is a scale parameter and k is the shape parameter. The shape parameter governs the tail behaviour of the distribution, the sub-families defined by $\xi = 0$, $\xi > 0$ and $\xi < 0$ correspond to the type I, II and III respectively. By default, in the *pyextremes* library the distribution is automatically selected as the best between GEVD and Gumbel using the AIC metric. Note that the AIC value decreases as the goodness-of-fit increases (see Equation 2):

$$AIC = 2k - 2\ln(L) \quad (2)$$

where L is the maximum likelihood (goodness of fit) and k is the number of parameters (which means complexity, in terms of variable interactions), (Bozdogan, 1987). This criterion is normally used to compare linear regression models, the one with the lowest AIC gives the best fit, the absolute value is not important. The log-likelihood value is also used to compare models but using a hypothesis test.

There is no single model that fits the wave data perfectly, in fact, the idea has always been to compare the goodness of fit for different models and distributions. Additionally, other estimation methods have been used in order to obtain only the variability of the parameters mentioned above (see *Figure 4.4* in *Section 4.1*). The method used is the Markov Chain Monte Carlo (MCMC), implemented through the *Emcee* library in Python (Foreman-Mackey, 2016)

Then, following the *pyextremes* library, the return periods of the extracted extreme values are estimated. The return period indicates the duration of time corresponding to the probability that a given value exceeds at least once within a year. In our study, we look at the values of wave height.

Extreme events extracted by the BM method are assigned to exceedance probabilities using the following formula:

$$P = \frac{r - \alpha}{n + 1 - \alpha - \beta} \quad (3)$$

where r corresponds to the rank of extreme values (ordered from the most extreme to the least), n is the number of extreme values, α and β are the empirical plotting position parameters. P corresponds to a probability of exceedance of a value with a rank r in a given time period with duration t/n , where t is the total duration of series. Because the method of BM has been used with a block size of 1 year, then the t/n becomes 1 and the return period in years can be estimated as $1/P$.

Return periods are calculated as:

$$R = 1/P/\lambda \quad (4)$$

where R corresponds to the return period as a multiple of one year (typical return period size), P is the calculated exceedance probability and λ is the rate of extreme events:

$$\lambda = \frac{\text{return period size}}{\text{block size}} \quad (5)$$

Finally, the return period and the diagnostic graph have been plotted (see Figures 4.6 and 4.7 in section 4.1).

3.3 Morphology

Sediment samples at the emerged beach were taken (see Table 1 and Figure 2.1) the 19th July 2019. A sieving analysis was performed by the researchers of the Odessa State Environmental University (OSENУ) to determine the particle size distribution (Figure 3.9).

Table 1. Sediment sample locations at Dniester emerged beach.

	Latitude	Longitude
Karolino-Bugaz	46.143462°	30.542696°
Solnechnoe	46.113361°	30.504656°
Zatoka	46.065641°	30.458572°

Note: Sediment sample taken the 19th July 2019.

Figure 3.9: Granulometric curve from three locations on Dniester Barrier Beach: Karolino-Bugaz, Solnechnoe and Zatoka. For all granulometric fractions. Extracted on 07/19/2019.

After calculating the d₅₀ for each location using Equation 6 (Bardet, 1977), given the sandy nature of the coasts studied, the granulometric curve has been recalculated only considering the sand fraction (<2μm), see Figure 3.10 and Table 2.

$$D_{50} = d_i \left(\frac{d_{i+1}}{d_i} \right)^{(50-P_i)/(P_{i+1}-P_i)} \quad (6)$$

where d_i and d_{i+1} re the diameters corresponding to the percentages (%) passing P_i and P_{i+1} .

Figure 3.10: Granulometric curve from three locations on Dniester Barrier Beach: Karolino-Bugaz, Solnechnoe and Zatoka. Exclusively the sand fraction.

Table 2. Calculated D50 from three locations in the Dniester barrier beach.

	D_{50} all fractions	D_{50} sand fraction
Karolino-Bugaz	0.372	0.369
Solnechnoe	0.510	0.403
Zatoka	0.421	0.389

3.4 XBeach Model Description

XBeach is a two-dimensional open-source numerical model developed to simulate hydrodynamic and morphodynamic conditions on sandy coasts. In fact, the original model developed in the context of the Morphos project and the US Geological Survey, aimed to assess the impacts of hurricanes on sandy beaches. Nowadays the software has evolved to simulate more complex processes: from storm impacts on dunes and urbanized coastlines, to all types of beaches with gravel, coral fringes, vegetative buffering effects and some other specifications.

3.4.1 Installation

There are two ways to install the software: one is to download the original code from a repository, and the other is to download the pre-compiled version ("Release and source - XBeach 2022), a more user-friendly option if no advanced knowledge of software development is possessed. In addition, there are also four download versions depending on the characteristics and the objective to be achieved: the most basic version called Regular or Trunk Version, the version with MPI (Message Passing Interface) that allows to work in parallel (multiple processors), the NetCDF version that allows to generate outputs in *.nc* files (the most common output of oceanography fields), and the most complete version that combines MPI and NetCDF modules ("User manual",

2020). We use the last version since working in parallel greatly reduces computational time and the `.nc` files permit to work more comfortably between different interfaces, as for example MATLAB.

3.4.2 Input files

Different input files are needed to start running the model, which must be in the same directory for correct operation. The most important is the `params.txt` file, which contains all the information needed to run the model, such as the grid and topo-bathymetry, wave input, morphological input, time/duration of the storm to be simulated, the angle of orientation of the grid, the output variables, and so on. Figure 2.1Figure 3.11 shows a simplified view of the `params.txt` file.

```

%%% General %%%
bcfile      = Dniester.txt
xfile       = x.grd
yfile       = y.grd
depfile     = bed.dep
wavemodel   = surfbeat
tintg       = 3600
tintm       = 3600
tstart      = 0
tstop       = 72000
thetamax    = 110
thetamin    = 90
dtheta      = 5
wbctype     = jonstable
xori        = 0
yori        = 0
alfa        = 0
D50         = 0.00042

%%% Output variables %%%

nglobalvar  = 4
zb
zs
sedero
wetz

```

Figure 3.11: Screenshot of a simplified case of the `paramax.txt` file needed to run XBeach.

There are many variables that can be modified in this file, but the most important parameters are the following:

- **xfile** and **yfile**: to generate the 2-D mesh, as well as specify the domain width (**nx**, **ny**).
- **depfile**: a depth file, which have to match with `xfile` and `yfile`.
- **tstop**: determine the time duration of the event (in seconds).
- **thetamin**, **thetamax**, **dtheta**: determine the minimum and maximum angle and width per bin, respectively.
- **wbctype**, **bcfile**: used to select the boundary conditions format and file itself with the information.

There are lots of other parameters that can be specified, although it is recommended to leave the default values ("User manual", 2020). The output variables are also specified in the example case on Figure 3.11, there are four: `zb` is the bed level, `zs` the water level, `wetz` have two possible values

in each node (0 or 1), dry or humid respectively, and *sedero*, which also have two values, sedimentation or erosion. All this variables and parameters are stored in a file called *xbeach.log*.

3.4.3 Grid characteristics

There are three very important things to keep in mind when generating the grid. Firstly, the three main files (*xfile*, *yfile* and *depfile*) have to maintain consistency in the positions of each matrix. Secondly, the x axis must be always perpendicular to the coast, while the y axis is parallel to it. This coordinate system is defined relative to world coordinates (x_w , y_w) through the origin (x_{ori} , y_{ori}) and the orientation *alfa* (Figure 3.12). Finally, the starting point of the grid has to coincide with the initial value of the files since, given the nature of the simulation, this point will always be in the offshore zone. As a general rule this point is located at the bottom left corner of the mesh.

Figure 3.12: Schematic representation of the orientation of the grid with respect to the coastline. Extracted from the *XBeach manual*, by Roelvink, 2010, p.11.

3.4.4 Hydrodynamic conditions

To generate the hydrodynamic conditions file there are three modes to work with:

- **Stationary**: efficiently solving wave-averaged equations but neglecting infragravity wave, has a reasonable computational cost.
- **Surfbeat**: the short-wave variations on the wave group scale (short wave envelope) and the long waves associated with them are resolved

- **Non-hydrostatic**: combine the non-linear shallow water equations with a pressure correction term, allowing to model the propagation and decay of individual waves. Also takes a long time to calculate it.

In this work the surfbeat mode is used because of its better strategy and implementation in most scenarios. It is necessary to find a balance between the desired resolution, the computational time and the study area. The surfbeat mode is defined by the *wavemodel* parameter, the format in which the waves are introduced is specified by the *wbctype* parameter, in this case *jons_table* where each row includes different wave conditions with the following order:

$$\langle Hm0 \rangle \langle Tp \rangle \langle mainang \rangle \langle gammajsp \rangle \langle s \rangle \langle duration \rangle \langle dbtc \rangle$$

where $Hm0$ is the significant wave height (m), Tp is the peak period (s), $mainang$ is the wave direction ($^\circ$), $gammajsp$ is the spectrum factor (3.3 by default), s is the directional coefficient of the spectrum (10 by default), $duration$ corresponds to the total time the wave conditions last (s) and $dbtc$ refers to how often these conditions occur at the boundary (s).

The relation between the significant wave height and the water depth has been also considered. The XBeach model works correctly in the green area of the graph in Figure 3.13. In our case, the wave height to water depth ratio is greater than 1/5.

Figure 3.13: Significant wave height to water depth ratio (H_s/h) for a correct operation of XBeach.. Adaptation from "Short Course: XBeach Modelling, Coastal Dynamics 2021" presented by Robert McCall, Ellen Quataert and Floortje Roelvink (Deltares).

3.4.5 Running the model

Once everything is ready, the model can be started by clicking on the executable or by command line if MPI is used (there is also a possibility with MATLAB toolbox for XBeach). When finished, in the present case where the MPI + NetCDF version has been used, the outputs of the model are found in an *.nc* file where all the organised information can be found. Figure 3.14 shows the file structure visualised through MATLAB, where *globalx* and *globaly* refer to the grid coordinates, *globaltime* to the total time simulation, and *zb* is the bed level. Each variable has four parameters: size, dimensions, datatype and attributes (metadata).

```

globalx
  Size:      2474x3266
  Dimensions: nx,ny
  Datatype:  double
  Attributes:
              units      = 'm'
              long_name   = 'local x coordinate'
              standard_name = 'projection_x_coordinate'
              axis        = 'X'

globaly
  Size:      2474x3266
  Dimensions: nx,ny
  Datatype:  double
  Attributes:
              units      = 'm'
              long_name   = 'local y coordinate'
              standard_name = 'projection_y_coordinate'
              axis        = 'Y'

globaltime
  Size:      1x1
  Dimensions: globaltime
  Datatype:  double
  Attributes:
              units      = 's'
              axis        = 'T'
              standard_name = 'time'

zb
  Size:      2474x3266x1
  Dimensions: nx,ny,globaltime
  Datatype:  double
  Attributes:
              coordinates = 'globalx globaly'
              units      = 'm'
              standard_name = 'altitude'
              long_name   = 'bed level'
              _FillValue  = -3.402823466385289e+38

```

Figure 3.14: NetCDF example file visualized by MATLAB.

3.5 Flooding and erosion definition

The term coastal flooding refers to the coverage by sea water of the dry coast. It can be temporary, when waves are considered, or permanent when the SLR is considered. Coastal flooding can be described as an amount of water reaching a certain point, commonly expressed as a thickness of water in cm or as the extension of land covered by water. Coastal Flooding in this study has been measured as the horizontal distance up which seawaters arrive with respect to the shoreline.

The term erosion can be seen, as coastal flooding, as a horizontal or vertical property. The shoreline retreat/advance is commonly used for the horizontal point of view, however, this does not necessary describe the magnitude of the bottom elevations. An example of this is the intense erosion that a dune can suffer after the pass for a storm which feeds the foreshore making the shoreline almost insensitive. A solution of such possible vagueness is the description of the process in the vertical dimension, that is, the amount of material eroded or accumulated at a certain point (a node in a grid) with respect to an initial stage. This last definition has been the way of measuring erosion/accretion in the study.

3.6 Modelled events

On 12 October 2016 a storm caused several damages in Odesa, 10 districts were affected by heavy rain, wind and storm surges. It was reported all over the news in the area. Bennadiy Leonidovich Trukhanov, the mayor of the Odesa region, reports that at least 105mm of rain were recorded in the 24h of 12-13 October (Davies, 2016). At this time of year, the monthly average is usually below 30mm. He also recorded damages to 1,500 trees. The State Emergency Service (SES) of Ukraine reported the flooding of 55 houses and the death of 3 people. More than 250 emergency personnel with 44 vehicles and 9 water pumps were deployed to deal with the multitude of flooded infrastructure. See Figure 3.15: Storm of 12 October 2016 at the south of the Dniester barrier beach (Zatoka). to have a visual overview of storm waves reaching the beach.

On 13 June 2015 was inaugurated the first kilometre of what was to become Europe's largest promenade, 12 km long and 6 m wide (Wier, 2015). The storm caused the promenade to collapse and covered it almost entirely with sand (Figure 3.16). The storm had a greater impact on Zatoka, causing flooding of private houses and the several scenario was in Primorskaya Street roadway (Zatoka, n.d.).

Figure 3.15: Storm of 12 October 2016 at the south of the Dniester barrier beach (Zatoka).

Figure 3.16: Damages caused by the storm of 12 October 2016 in Dniester barrier beach (Zatoka). Photo taken by A. Anastasov.

The storm of 12 October was chosen for the XBeach simulation with the main objective of making a qualitative comparison of the damage caused on the barrier beach. According to ERA 5 data, at 11:00h the maximum significant wave height reached 3.37 m at about 25 km offshore, with an associated period and direction of 6.65 s and 106.17° respectively. The total simulated time has been 20 hours, from 01:00 h to 21:00 h. Table 3 shows the hydrodynamic conditions used in this work.

Table 3. Hydrodynamic conditions simulated for the XBeach model.

Time (h)	Hs (m)	T (m)	Dir (°)
12/10/2016 1:00	2,25	5,6	110,4
12/10/2016 2:00	2,38	5,7	109,4
12/10/2016 3:00	2,49	5,8	108,2
12/10/2016 4:00	2,68	6,0	106,8
12/10/2016 5:00	2,77	6,1	105,7
12/10/2016 6:00	2,87	6,2	104,3
12/10/2016 7:00	3,01	6,3	102,8
12/10/2016 8:00	3,14	6,3	102,1
12/10/2016 9:00	3,23	6,5	102,8
12/10/2016 10:00	3,33	6,5	104,3
12/10/2016 11:00	3,37	6,6	106,1
12/10/2016 12:00	3,34	6,6	107,7
12/10/2016 13:00	3,26	6,7	108,3
12/10/2016 14:00	3,18	6,6	108,2
12/10/2016 15:00	3,09	6,6	108,1
12/10/2016 16:00	2,98	6,6	108,5
12/10/2016 17:00	2,86	6,5	109,3
12/10/2016 18:00	2,76	6,5	111,1
12/10/2016 19:00	2,72	6,4	114,4
12/10/2016 20:00	2,77	6,3	119,0
12/10/2016 21:00	2,91	6,3	125,4

Note: The red box represents the peak of the storm.

The extreme event has been simulated for two different mean water level (MWL) scenarios in the same wave conditions. In the first one, the initial water level parameter is $z_{s0} = 0$, while in the second is $z_{s0} = 0.7$ (Table 4).

The MWL can be understood as the combination of the astronomical tide, the storm surge and the sea level rise induced by climate change. Due to its nature, the astronomical tide is not a random component although it has to be treated as a stochastic variable assuming that it is not time-correlated with storms. A value of 0.14 m is considered following Medvedev (2018). Moreover, high values of surge are not necessarily linked to storms. No information is available for the storm of October 2016 and because of that the reference simulation has been done only considering the wave contribution. However, the simulation of a future scenario has as a main objective determine the maximum possible impact over the barrier and because of this the worst-case approach has been used. The storm of October 2016 has a relatively low return period, of about 1.5 years, and it has been assumed to have a pattern similar to the one observed in the Spanish Mediterranean

Sea, because of that a value of 0.26 m has been selected. Finally, the climate change signal is introduced following Tătui et al. (2019).

The so obtained 0.7 m has to be understood as a high probable value for the year 2100 and can be explained by the works found in the literature review. The last Assessment report published by the IPCC (2021) determines a SLR rate of 10mm/year and 4.6 mm/year for the SSP5-8.5 and SSP2-4.5 respectively. As it can be seen the selection of 0.7 m is a highly probable value.

Table 4. Analysed cases from the storm of 12 October 2016 according to the MWL scenario.

Storm of 12/10/2016	SLR (m)	Astronomical Tides (m)	Storm surge (m)	Initial water level / z_{s0} (m)
Case 1: Present	0	0	0	0
Case 2: 100-year RP	0.3	0.14	0.26	0,7

4. Results and discussion

4.1 Extreme Wave Regime

Figure 4.1 shows the wave rose diagram of direction reaching the Dniester barrier beach and obtained from the ERA5 wave dataset. As it can be seen, the highest wave heights come from the ENE sector.

Figure 4.1: Wave rose of the Effective Significant Wave Height (45° - 215°).

Therefore, with this reduced dataset the AMM is applied, resulting in a total of 43 maximum values (Figure 4.2). See ANNEX 2 for the whole set of extreme values.

Figure 4.2: Annual maximum significant wave heights taken from ERA5 dataset from 1979 to 2021.

Next step is to fit the GEVD model to the extreme data values (Equation 1) using the MLE method. Based on the AIC value turns out to be the Gumbel distribution that best fits the data. This means that shape parameter of the fitted model is 0. The scale parameter is 0.44, the location is 3.48, the loglikelihood value is -34.14 and the AIC is 72.58 Figure 4.3 shows a complete diagnostic of the model.

Univariate Extreme Value Analysis			

Source Data			

Data label: Signifiacnt Wave Height - Hs(m)	Size:	376,054	
Start:	January 1979	End:	November 2021

Extreme Values			

Count:	43	Extraction method:	BM
Type:	high	Block size:	365 days 05:49:12

Model			

Model:	MLE	Distribution:	gumbel_r
Log-likelihood:	-34.144	AIC:	72.588

Free parameters:	loc=3.489	Fixed parameters: All parameters are free	
	scale=0.447		

Figure 4.3: Model summary of EVA from Effective Significant Wave Height.

The estimates obtained by MCMC method show a large variability in the parameter samples, especially in the shape parameter, where the range of simulated values goes from -0.50 to 0.25 (Figure 4.4).

Figure 4.4: Trace plot of the GEVD parameters. The red line represents the mean of the evolution of the parameter samples obtained by MCMC simulation.

While the mean is centred very close to zero, given the uncertainty of the shape parameter, just as one could not reject the fit with the Gumbel distribution, neither for the Weibull distribution. Furthermore, looking at the marginal distribution of the shape parameter (Figure 4.5) it can be seen that there is a heavier tail for negative values than for positive, suggesting that both Weibull and Gumbel are a good choice.

Figure 4.5: Marginal density function of shape parameter (ξ).

The model diagnostic allows to inspect visually how good is the MLE model with the Gumbel distribution, if the obtained results are meaningful, and how confident can be with the estimated return values (Figure 4.6).

Figure 4.6: Model plot diagnostic. A) Return value plot, B) Probability density plot of Effective Significant Wave Height, C) Q-Q plot, and D) P-P plot.

The probability density plot (Figure 4.1.B) gives a visual idea of how the distribution describes the nature of the data. It shows the probability density function of the Gumbel distribution (Y-axis) vs the histogram of the data from the extracted extreme values (X-axis). As can be seen, the fit is good, except for some values in the centre, possibly due to the small amount of data as only the extreme values extracted by AMM are considered.

At first look the quantile-quantile (QQ) and percentile-percentile (PP) plots indicates a good fit, furthermore the R^2 values are very close to the unit and the p-value is zero. Figure 4.1.C shows QQ plots of significant wave height, which compares the quantiles of the data distribution with the quantiles of the standardized theoretical distribution of the GEVD Type I. For perfect

agreement, the sampled data should follow the 1:1 trend line and be centred on the mean. The comparison indicates that the model shows a tendency to over-predict the maximum values. This may be due to the lower frequency of extreme values, i.e. fewer data with large values of significant wave height. Figure 4.1.D shows PP plots of significant wave height, which in this case compares the empirical cumulative distribution function of the data set with a specific theoretical cumulative distribution function (Gumbel). In this case theoretical distribution models well the data distribution.

Figure 4.7: Estimation of Return Periods and the corresponding confidence intervals.

As the model has been fit to the data and having determined which distribution best represents the wave, the return periods are calculated from the exceedance probabilities (Figure 4.7). As it can be seen, all data are within the confidence bands, which means a good fit.

The maximum significant wave height for the effective directions corresponds to 5.46 m with an associated return period of 44 years (ANNEX A). The return levels for the 10, 50 and 100 years return periods are 4.49 m, 5.23 m and 5.54 m respectively (see Table 5).

Table 5. Significant wave heights and associated return periods for central, lower and upper confidence intervals.

Return Period	Return Value	Lower C.I.	Upper C.I.
2	3,65	3,51	3,83
3	3,89	3,69	4,10
4	4,04	3,81	4,29
5	4,15	3,90	4,42
10	4,49	4,15	4,82
25	4,91	4,47	5,32
50	5,23	4,71	5,70
100	5,54	4,95	6,08
250	5,95	5,26	6,59
500	6,26	5,49	6,97
1000	6,57	5,72	7,34

4.2 Flooding

The simulations were run for the two MWL scenarios as explained in section 3.6. The results obtained for each case in terms of flooding are presented here.

4.2.1 Case 1: MWL = 0 m

Figure 4.8 shows the beach state at different time lapse. As it can be seen, the very shallow nature of the foreshore makes the emergence of small areas during the first hours of simulation (from $t=1h$ to $t=6h$), however it has to be pointed out that most of them have a height less than $+0.005$ m (Figure 4.8.a). Such behaviour is due to the mismatch between the different spatial sources used to create the DEM and it disappears after the pass of the first waves crest, being fully submerged at hour $t=7h$ (Figure 4.8.c). Therefore, the first wave front generated offshore ($t = 1 h$) arrives at the south coast between 5 and 6 hours later whereas in the northern part of the barrier beach the waves arrive up to 7 hours later.

Figure 4.8: Comparison between the $t = 5 h$, $6 = h$ and $7 = h$ of the case 1 simulation (MWL = 0 m).

Figure 4.9 shows the incoming waves at $t=6$ h. As it can be seen that in the northern part the waves show long regular wave crests whereas in the southern part waves a short crested.

Figure 4.9: Incoming waves at $t = 6$ h for $MWL = 0m$.

This wave crest pattern could be explained by the non-homogeneous bathymetry, flat at the deeper zone at north ($\cong 12$ m) and with a steep slope close to the shoreline, whereas gentler in the shallow zone at the south. Figure 4.10 shows with a blue circle the southern area where the waves are short crested, while the north area where regular waves are observed is shown with a red circle.

Figure 4.10: Bathymetry of the study area. The blue circle indicates the steep slope, while the red circle indicates the gentler slope.

As it can be seen in Figure 4.11 and Figure 4.12 major flooding impact takes place at $t = 18$ h, especially in the narrowest zone (Figure 4.11.b2). This event corresponds to the peak of the storm, which starts at 11:00h at the boundary (see Table 3).

Figure 4.11: Flooding comparison between the wave arrived ($t = 7$ h) and the maximum intensity ($t = 18$ h) for the Case 1 - MWL = 0m.

Figure 4.12 shows the inundation lines for $t = 7$ h and $t = 18$ h. The flooding was fairly homogeneous along the coast, with an average of 7,19 m. The largest episode of overtopping occurred in the narrowest area near Slonechnoe, with a maximum flood of 100 m (right rectangle in Figure 4.12). On the other hand, in the Zatoka area the flooding was much lower (left rectangle in Figure 4.12), which can be explained by the existence of a submerged platform at 10 m depth (see blue circle in Figure 4.10) that triggers the wave energy dissipation due to bottom friction.

Figure 4.12: Flooding lines at $t = 7$ h and $t = 18$ h for the Case 1 - MWL = 0m. The black rectangles show the Zatoka area (left) and the narrowest Slonechnoe area (right).

4.2.2 Case 2: MWL = 0.7 m

The small elevations observed at the first time-steps of case 1 (MWL = 0 m) are not observed due to initial MWL condition of 0.7 m, Figure 4.13 shows the barrier states at the beginning and peak of the storm. As it can be seen, severe overtopping is detected at Slonechnoe area, where the barrier is narrow and lower.

Figure 4.13: Dniester flooding states at the beginning of the simulation ($t = 1$ h) and at the peak of the storm ($t = 18$ h) for case 2 (MWL = 0.7 m).

Figure 4.14 shows the inundation lines for $t = 1$ h and $t = 18$ h, where the mean flooding was 18 m and the maximum was 200 m, also in the narrow zone near Slonechnoe. In order to facilitate comparisons, Figure 4.15 shows the inundation lines for the two cases of MWL (0 m and 0.7 m). As it can be seen, the inundation patterns were quite similar in terms of affected areas, but with different magnitudes. Comparing the maximum intensity time steps ($t = 18$ h) of both cases (green line for MWL = 0 and black for MWL = 0.7 m) it was determined that the average inundation for the Dniester barrier beach was about 50 m, while the maximum flooded distance with respect to the shoreline was of 170 m (Table 6).

Figure 4.14: Flooding lines at $t = 7$ h and $t = 18$ h for the Case 2 - MWL = 0.7 m. The black rectangles show the Zatoka area (left) and the narrowest Slonechnoe area (right).

Figure 4.15: Flooding lines for MWL = 0 and MWL = 0.7 m. The two black rectangles show a zoom in the southern area near Zatoka and in the narrow area at the north.

Of the total analysed cases, the strongest inundation was 200 m in the low and narrow zone of the barrier beach for the simulation run with MWL = 0.7 at $t = 18$ h (black line in the right rectangle of Figure 4.15). See Table 6 to compare the flooding scenarios.

Table 6. Flooding scenarios comparasion.

Analysed Case	Mean Flooding (m)	Maximum Flooding (m)
A	7.19	18
B	100	200
C	50	170

A: MWL = 0 m at t = 7 h - MWL = 0 at t = 18 h

B: MWL = 0.7 m at t = 1 h - MWL = 0.7 at t = 18 h

C: MWL = 0 m at t = 18 h - MWL = 0.7 at t = 18 h

Figure 4.16 shows the exposure of the Dniester barrier to coastal flooding. The red circles represent the areas where flooding has a high potential to affect the existing infrastructures due to the combination of coastal squeezing (between 5 and 20 m) and the low elevation, less than 2.5 m. The blue areas of the figure indicate those sectors in which would not cause as much damage, mostly due to the presence of a wider beach in front between 50 and 250 m long, that is able to dissipate the incoming wave energy.

The red circle number 1 of Figure 4.16 is the sector in which major flooding was reported (Zatoka, Figure 3.15.). The results of case 1 do not show severe flooding for that area, however, the simulation only reflects the contribution of waves, thus, if MWL is considered (Case 2) it can be seen that the inundation is significantly greater (Figure 4.15). Although Case 2 represents a climate change scenario it also ca be considered as an extreme present event scenario in which a moderate wave storm reaches the coast during extremely high mean water levels. The overall results suggest that in the coming years this area will be very vulnerable to extreme events.

In zone 2 there is no more than 5m between the houses and the sea, in Figure 4.12 a noticeable difference can be seen between the two flood lines above the inlet. Suggesting that the infrastructures suffered major flooding. In this area there is no information for comparison.

Zone 3, mentioned above, is the most affected in all the analysed cases. Table 6 shows the maximum flooding for each scenario, which all coincide in this narrow zone of the bar.

Figure 4.16: Map of the Dniester barrier beach. The red circles show the areas with infrastructures vulnerable to flooding, the blue bands represent the unbuilt areas with the largest beach widths.

4.2 Erosion

4.2.1 Case 1: MWL = 0 m

There were four distinct zones where erosion/sedimentation processes occur: the inlet (*), the open sea shoreline (**), the estuary shoreline (***) and the submarine bar (****). These zones can be seen in *Figure 4.17*, where their location is shown.

Figure 4.17: Location of the four differenced zones against the topography of the barrier beach for MWL = 0 m: Inlet (), open sea shoreline (**), estuary shoreline (***) and submarine bar (****).*

The erosion and sedimentation magnitudes of the four zones is shown in different perspectives, in *Figure 4.18* and *4.19*. Up to the zero line indicates sedimentation (tends to yellow colour), and below the zero line indicates erosion (tends to dark blue).

Figure 4.18: Three-dimensional distribution of sedimentation/erosion process of the four differenced zones for MWL = 0 m; Inlet (), open sea shoreline (**), estuary shoreline (***) and submarine bar (****).*

Figure 4.19: Erosion/Sedimentation magnitudes (m) for MWL = 0 m.

Most of erosion and sedimentation processes were concentrated at the inlet (*), see the highest and lowest values in Figure 4.18. This is due to the abrupt change in slope, going from -10 m to -2 m in a very short distance (marked with a black arrow below the bridge in Figure 4.20). Sedimentation in this area was about 4m (see Figure 4.19). This could have several consequences on the estuary dynamics, closing the channel connection, changing the saline composition of the water and causing environmental problems such as loss of biodiversity.

Figure 4.20: Zoom in the inlet area showing the steep slope marked with an arrow. Extracted from the nautical chart provided by Odessa State Environmental University (OSENУ), ANNEX A.

Along the northern part of the inlet there is an erosion pattern in the submerged bar (****) and sedimentation in the emerged coast zone (**), which coincides with the flooded line (see blue arrows in Figure 4.16).

Highly values of sedimentation are observed along the estuary shoreline (***). Since this is not the area of interest for this work, a rough smoothing was done causing an abrupt slope between the -1.5 elevation of the estuary and the coastline (explained in Section 3.1)

Sedimentation and erosion processes were not particularly noticeable along the barrier beach, with the exception of the inlet, where the highest values of both processes are concentrated.

4.2.2 Case 1: MWL = 0.7 m

In this second case where sea level is higher, sedimentation and erosion processes dominate over a much larger area compared to the case of MWL = 0 (Figure 4.16 vs Figure 4.21). This occurs especially along the open sea shoreline (**).

Figure 4.21: Location of the four differenced zones against the topography of the barrier beach for MWL = 0.7 m: Inlet (*), open sea shoreline (**), estuary shoreline (***) and submarine bar (****).

The three-dimensional distribution of both processes can be seen in Figure 4.22, where the dominance of erosion/sedimentation at the inlet is again evident. The magnitudes are practically the same between the two cases analysed (Figure 4.23).

Figure 4.22: Sedimentation/Erosion in the four differenced zones for MWL = 0.7 m; Inlet (*), open sea shoreline (**), estuary shoreline (***) and submarine bar (****).

Figure 4.23: Erosion/Sedimentation magnitudes (m) for MWL = 0.7 m.

This situation of sediment accumulation on the shore can be visually corroborated by the photos of the news reports in *Section 3.6*. Figure 3.15 shows the storm situation, where the promenade was overtopped and contributed large amounts of sediment, while Figure 3.16 shows the situation after the storm is over, with the promenade partly broken and a large part covered by sand.

4.3 Future Work

Considering the literature of the EVA, where the most used distribution in coastal and ocean engineering is the Weibull (Goda et al. 2010), it is also reasonable to use this distribution since it decreases much faster in the positive side than Fréchet and Gumbel. This makes sense in studies of physical phenomena such as waves, where we could never expect wave heights of thousands of meters, for example. This opens the door for future studies to compare different methods such as Peak Over Threshold (POT), models and statistical techniques to find the one that best describes the data presented in this study.

One line of improvement would be to improve the mesh and to be able to represent it in a GIS platform. Furthermore, it would be interesting to be able to better reflect the reality of the area, for example by making the coastal infrastructures such as the promenade and buildings more rigid. In this case it has not been a problem due to the low intensity of the modelled event. In situations where longer return periods are modelled then it would be more critical.

Lastly, it would be useful to simulate more events for the current conditions (systematic events, artificially constructing a storm and running it with XBeach). Then it would be possible to do the projection of the same event to the climate change scenarios.

5. Conclusions

The vulnerability of the Dniester beach has been evaluated through the use of the numerical model XBeach. A storm event with different two mean water levels has been modelled.

From the available data, ERA5 reanalysis time series, a good fit has been obtained using the annual maximums method (AMM). The Gumbel no-exceedance distribution function adequately represents the storm regime of the area. The ENE, E, and in a lesser magnitude SSW wave direction, have a significant impact on the Dniester barrier beach. The storm intensities of the ERA5 series are actually low compared to the fetch limited seas such as the Mediterranean. Being the maximum wave height modelled of about 5 m, with an associated return periods of 43 years.

Hydrodynamic modelling of the October 2016 storm has revealed the influence of bathymetry on hydrodynamic propagation patterns. Flat deep areas in the north have been associated with long-crested waves, while more irregular bathymetric contours in the south coincide with short-crested waves.

Three major areas have been identify regarding to coastal flooding. The highest values are observed in the narrowest zone at the north, Solnechnoe area, where also the level of the barrier is lower. At the vicinity of the northers site of the inlet major inundation are also observed. At the south, in the Zatoka area, flooding is observed when the mean water level contribution is considered. This last two sectors also present infrastructures, such as an sea front promenades very close to the shoreline.

Mean water level plays an important role on the inundation results, exacerbating the intensity in the previous mentioned areas.

Regarding to erosion/accumulation it has been seen that erosion is taken place at the foreshore along the barrier, whereas sedimentation is taken place in the upper emerged part, in coincident with flooding. Major erosion and accumulation are located at the inlet, where a navigation channel with a depth of 10 m connect the estuary with the open sea. This behaviour can be explained by the sharp slope gradients generated by the canal.

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ANNEX A - Nautical chart provided by Odessa State Environmental University (OSENU)

ANNEX B. Estimated Return Periods from the extreme values extracted using AMM.

Time from 1979 to 2021	Extreme wave values (m)	Exceedance probability	Return period (yr)
19/2/1979 8:00	4,63	0,12	8,60
3/1/1980 17:00	3,20	0,86	1,16
10/11/1981 4:00	4,96	0,05	21,50
21/3/1982 2:00	3,27	0,81	1,23
29/11/1983 6:00	3,37	0,70	1,43
10/2/1984 8:00	3,74	0,47	2,15
6/1/1985 3:00	3,38	0,65	1,54
25/1/1986 12:00	3,85	0,37	2,69
19/1/1987 9:00	3,69	0,49	2,05
1/2/1988 7:00	4,88	0,07	14,33
27/2/1989 5:00	3,28	0,74	1,34
1/12/1990 4:00	2,82	1,00	1,00
16/2/1991 10:00	4,00	0,28	3,58
18/11/1992 3:00	3,76	0,44	2,26
30/11/1993 20:00	4,40	0,16	6,14
22/10/1994 7:00	3,62	0,53	1,87
5/11/1995 20:00	4,52	0,14	7,17
21/11/1996 9:00	3,27	0,79	1,26
20/3/1997 2:00	4,84	0,09	10,75
23/1/1998 1:00	4,37	0,19	5,38
23/2/1999 11:00	3,77	0,42	2,39
1/1/2000 3:00	3,46	0,60	1,65
26/2/2001 15:00	3,49	0,58	1,72
1/12/2002 18:00	3,28	0,77	1,30
5/2/2003 14:00	3,43	0,63	1,59
29/1/2004 7:00	3,01	0,98	1,02
25/11/2005 9:00	3,50	0,56	1,79
6/1/2006 4:00	3,24	0,84	1,19
23/3/2007 19:00	3,95	0,30	3,31
3/1/2008 17:00	4,14	0,23	4,30
16/12/2009 7:00	3,68	0,51	1,95
6/1/2010 9:00	3,19	0,91	1,10
17/12/2011 17:00	3,92	0,33	3,07
7/2/2012 19:00	5,46	0,02	43,00
1/10/2013 18:00	4,04	0,26	3,91
25/10/2014 18:00	3,91	0,35	2,87
31/1/2015 11:00	4,32	0,21	4,78
12/10/2016 11:00	3,37	0,67	1,48
26/9/2017 23:00	3,14	0,93	1,08
19/11/2018 12:00	3,84	0,40	2,53
21/11/2019 18:00	3,28	0,72	1,39
10/2/2020 20:00	3,19	0,88	1,13
25/1/2021 16:00	3,10	0,95	1,05

ANNEX C - Python code for data pre-processing and extreme value analysis (EVA).

The code has been moved to Google Colab for anyone who would like to continue the study can. For its use it is important to put the file "ERA5_1979_to_2021.txt" in the corresponding directory. The link is the one below (open for UPC members):

<https://colab.research.google.com/drive/16esl7CMBW6xwL4agpLFasmq8lYK1b6zi?hl=es#scrollTo=CCszK8-tzomk>

ERA 5 dataset:

<https://drive.google.com/file/d/1IH6zRN9kVH9MNefMpeb0CNE4d6g6j94O/view?usp=sharing>

```
import numpy as np
import matplotlib.pyplot as plt
import pandas as pd
import seaborn as sb

!pip install windrose
from windrose import WindroseAxes
from windrose import WindAxes
```

Looking in indexes: <https://pypi.org/simple>, <https://us-python.pkg.dev/colab-wheels/public/simple/>

Collecting windrose

Downloading windrose-1.7.0-py3-none-any.whl (11 kB)

Requirement already satisfied: matplotlib>=3 in

/usr/local/lib/python3.7/dist-packages (from windrose) (3.2.2)

Requirement already satisfied: numpy>=1.19 in /usr/local/lib/python3.7/dist-packages (from windrose) (1.21.6)

Requirement already satisfied: pyparsing!=2.0.4,!=2.1.2,!=2.1.6,>=2.0.1 in /usr/local/lib/python3.7/dist-packages (from matplotlib>=3->>windrose) (3.0.9)

Requirement already satisfied: python-dateutil>=2.1 in

/usr/local/lib/python3.7/dist-packages (from matplotlib>=3->>windrose) (2.8.2)

Requirement already satisfied: cyclor>=0.10 in /usr/local/lib/python3.7/dist-packages (from matplotlib>=3->>windrose) (0.11.0)

Requirement already satisfied: kiwisolver>=1.0.1 in

/usr/local/lib/python3.7/dist-packages (from matplotlib>=3->>windrose) (1.4.3)

Requirement already satisfied: typing-extensions in

/usr/local/lib/python3.7/dist-packages (from kiwisolver>=1.0.1->matplotlib>=3->>windrose) (4.1.1)

Requirement already satisfied: six>=1.5 in /usr/local/lib/python3.7/dist-packages (from python-dateutil>=2.1->matplotlib>=3->>windrose) (1.15.0)

Installing collected packages: windrose

Successfully installed windrose-1.7.0

Load the data from ERA 5 hourly data on single levels from 1959 to present.

```
mostrar_plots = True
```

```
df = pd.read_csv('/ERA5_1979_to_2021.txt', sep="\t", header=None)
print(df)
```

```
      0      1      2      3
0  01-Jan-1979 00:00:00  1.941813  5.275631  193.194329
1  01-Jan-1979 01:00:00  2.086149  5.504405  197.100159
2  01-Jan-1979 02:00:00  2.135054  5.711151  199.747993
3  01-Jan-1979 03:00:00  2.166500  5.863779  202.242010
4  01-Jan-1979 04:00:00  2.159160  5.988005  203.999908
...
376049  24-Nov-2021 17:00:00      NaN      NaN      NaN
376050  24-Nov-2021 18:00:00      NaN      NaN      NaN
376051  24-Nov-2021 19:00:00      NaN      NaN      NaN
376052  24-Nov-2021 20:00:00      NaN      NaN      NaN
376053  24-Nov-2021 21:00:00      NaN      NaN      NaN
```

```
[376054 rows x 4 columns]
```

```
time = df[0]
Hs = df[1]
Ts = df[2]
Ds = df[3]
E = (Hs ** 2) * Ts
```

```
variables = pd.DataFrame({'Significat Wave Height - Hs(m)': Hs,
                          'Mean wave period - T(s)': Ts,
                          'Mean wave direction - Dr(°)': Ds,
                          'Wave Energy': E})
```

```
dataa = pd.to_datetime(time)
```

```
variables['Time (years) - From 1979 to 2021'] = pd.Series(time)
time2 = variables['Time (years) - From 1979 to 2021']
serie2 = variables.set_index('Time (years) - From 1979 to 2021')
temp = serie2.loc['12-Oct-2016 01:00:00':'12-Oct-2016 21:00:00']
serie_orig = serie2
Hs_all = serie_orig[['Significat Wave Height - Hs(m)']]
```

Data Visualisation

```
# Hist 2
plt.figure(0)
plt.hist(Hs, bins='auto', color='#ec7c34')
plt.title("Histogram of Significant height of combined wind waves and swell")
plt.xlabel("swh (m)")
# xlim([0 374016])
plt.ylabel("Frequency")
plt.grid(axis='both', alpha=0.5)
if mostrar_plots:
    plt.show()
plt.close()
```



```
# Hs
plt.figure(1)
plt.plot(dataa, Hs)
plt.title(" Significant height of combined wind waves and swell")
plt.xlabel("Time from 1979 to 2021 (years)")
# xlim([0 374016])
plt.ylabel(" swh (m)")
plt.grid()
if mostrar_plots:
    plt.show()
plt.close()
```



```
# Ts
plt.figure(2)
plt.plot(dataa, Ts)
plt.title("Mean wave period")
plt.xlabel("Time from 1979 to 2021 (years)")
# xlim([0 374016])
plt.ylabel(" mwp (s)")
plt.grid()
if mostrar_plots:
    plt.show()
plt.close()
```



```

# Ds
plt.figure(3)
plt.plot(dataa, Ds, '.')
plt.title("Mean wave direction - Dr(°)")
plt.xlabel("Time from 1979 to 2021 (years)")
# xlim([0 374016])
plt.ylabel(" mwd (°)")
plt.grid()
if mostrar_plots:
    plt.show()
plt.close()

```



```

# E
plt.figure(4)
plt.plot(dataa, E)
plt.title("Wave Energy")
plt.xlabel("Time from 1979 to 2021 (years)")
# xlim([0 374016])
plt.ylabel(" Energy (m$^2$.s) ")
plt.grid()
if mostrar_plots:
    plt.show()
plt.close()

```


Wave Rose

```
# WindRose Hs
plt.figure(7)
ax = WindroseAxes.from_ax()
ax.bar(Ds, Hs, bins=np.arange(0, 4, 0.5))
ax.set_legend()
plt.title('Significant Wave Height - Hs(m)')
ax.set_xticklabels(['E', 'NE', 'N', 'NW', 'W', 'SW', 'S', 'SE'])
if mostrar_plots:
    plt.show()
plt.close()
```

<Figure size 432x288 with 0 Axes>


```
# WindRose P
plt.figure(8)
ax = WindroseAxes.from_ax()
ax.bar(Ds, Ts, bins=np.arange(0, 9, 1))
ax.set_legend()
plt.title('Mean Wave Period - T(s)')
ax.set_xticklabels(['E', 'NE', 'N', 'NW', 'W', 'SW', 'S', 'SE'])
if mostrar_plots:
    plt.show()
plt.close()
```

<Figure size 432x288 with 0 Axes>


```
# WindRose E
plt.figure(9)
ax = WindroseAxes.from_ax()
ax.bar(Ds, E, bins=np.arange(0, 40, 5))
ax.set_legend()
plt.title('Wave Energy- E(m$^2$.s)')
ax.set_xticklabels(['E', 'NE', 'N', 'NW', 'W', 'SW', 'S', 'SE'])
if mostrar_plots:
    plt.show()
plt.close()
```

<Figure size 432x288 with 0 Axes>

Effective Directions reaching the Dniester barrier beach

```
new_Ds = []
new_Hs = []
new_Ts = []
new_E = []
for i in range(len(Ds)):
    index_Ds = Ds[i]
    index_Hs = Hs[i]
    index_Ts = Ts[i]
    index_E = E[i]

    if 45 < index_Ds < 215:
        new_Ds.append(index_Ds)
```

```

n_Hs = new_Hs.append(index_Hs)
n_Ts = new_Ts.append(index_Ts)
n_E = new_E.append(index_E)

for i in serie2:
    print(i, type(i))
    # print(serie2[i])
    if i == 'Mean wave direction - Dr(°)':
        for j in range(0, len(serie2[i])):
            # print(j)
            if not 45 < serie2[i][j] < 215:
                serie2[i][j] = 0
                # print(serie[i][j])

for i in serie2:
    print(i, type(i))
    # print(serie2[i])
    if not i == 'Mean wave direction - Dr(°)':
        for j in range(0, len(serie2[i])):
            # print(i,j)
            if serie2['Mean wave direction - Dr(°)'][j] == 0:
                serie2[i][j] = 0
                # print(serie[i][j])

dir_efect = serie2
max_dir_efect = max(dir_efect['Signifiacnt Wave Height - Hs(m)'])
dir_efect_ = dir_efect.loc['07-Feb-2012 11:00:00':'09-Feb-2012 12:00:00']
maxim_temporal = dir_efect.loc['07-Feb-2012 18:00:00']

D_efect = dir_efect['Mean wave direction - Dr(°)']
H_efect = dir_efect['Signifiacnt Wave Height - Hs(m)']
T_efect = dir_efect['Mean wave period - T(s)']
E_efect = dir_efect['Wave Energy']

Signifiacnt Wave Height - Hs(m) <class 'str'>
Mean wave period - T(s) <class 'str'>
Mean wave direction - Dr(°) <class 'str'>
Wave Energy <class 'str'>
Signifiacnt Wave Height - Hs(m) <class 'str'>
Mean wave period - T(s) <class 'str'>
Mean wave direction - Dr(°) <class 'str'>
Wave Energy <class 'str'>

#Effective Wave Rose

plt.figure()
ax = WindroseAxes.from_ax()
ax.bar(new_Ds, new_Hs, bins=np.arange(0, 4, 0.5))
plt.title('Effective Significant Wave Height- Hs(m)')
ax.set_legend()
ax.set_xticklabels(['E', 'NE', 'N', 'NW', 'W', 'SW', 'S', 'SE'])
if mostrar_plots:
    plt.show()
plt.close()

<Figure size 432x288 with 0 Axes>

```



```
plt.figure()
ax = WindroseAxes.from_ax()
ax.bar(new_Ds, new_E, bins=np.arange(0, 40, 5))
ax.set_legend()
plt.title('Effective Wave Energy - E(m$^2$.s)')
ax.set_xticklabels(['E', 'NE', 'N', 'NW', 'W', 'SW', 'S', 'SE'])
if mostrar_plots:
    plt.show()
plt.close()
```

<Figure size 432x288 with 0 Axes>


```
plt.figure()
ax = WindroseAxes.from_ax()
ax.bar(new_Ds, new_Ts, bins=np.arange(0, 9, 1))
ax.set_legend()
plt.title('Effective Mean Wave Period - T(s)')
ax.set_xticklabels(['E', 'NE', 'N', 'NW', 'W', 'SW', 'S', 'SE'])
if mostrar_plots:
    plt.show()
plt.close()
```

<Figure size 432x288 with 0 Axes>


```
print(H_effect, H_effect.shape, type(H_effect))
H_effect.to_csv('H_effect.csv', header=True, index=True)
```

```
Time (years) - From 1979 to 2021
01-Jan-1979 00:00:00    1.941813
01-Jan-1979 01:00:00    2.086149
01-Jan-1979 02:00:00    2.135054
01-Jan-1979 03:00:00    2.166500
01-Jan-1979 04:00:00    2.159160
```

```
...
24-Nov-2021 17:00:00    0.000000
24-Nov-2021 18:00:00    0.000000
24-Nov-2021 19:00:00    0.000000
24-Nov-2021 20:00:00    0.000000
24-Nov-2021 21:00:00    0.000000
```

```
Name: Signifiacnt Wave Height - Hs(m), Length: 376054, dtype: float64
(376054,) <class 'pandas.core.series.Series'>
```

Extreme Value Analysis - (EVA)

```
!pip install pyextremes
```

```
import pyextremes
import pandas as pd
from pyextremes import EVA
from pyextremes import get_extremes
from pyextremes.plotting import plot_extremes
from pyextremes import get_extremes, get_return_periods

from pyextremes import __version__, EVA, get_extremes
from pyextremes.models import Emcee
from pyextremes.plotting import (
    plot_extremes,
    pyextremes_rc,
    plot_trace,
    plot_corner,
)
```

```
Looking in indexes: https://pypi.org/simple, https://us-python.pkg.dev/colab-
wheels/public/simple/
```

```
Collecting pyextremes
```

```
  Downloading pyextremes-2.0.0-py3-none-any.whl (49 kB)
```

```

ent already satisfied: numpy in /usr/local/lib/python3.7/dist-packages (from
pyextremes) (1.21.6)
Collecting emcee>=3.0
  Downloading emcee-3.1.2-py2.py3-none-any.whl (46 kB)
ent already satisfied: matplotlib in /usr/local/lib/python3.7/dist-packages
(from pyextremes) (3.2.2)
Requirement already satisfied: scipy in /usr/local/lib/python3.7/dist-
packages (from pyextremes) (1.4.1)
Requirement already satisfied: pandas in /usr/local/lib/python3.7/dist-
packages (from pyextremes) (1.3.5)
Requirement already satisfied: pyparsing!=2.0.4,!=2.1.2,!=2.1.6,>=2.0.1 in
/usr/local/lib/python3.7/dist-packages (from matplotlib->pyextremes) (3.0.9)
Requirement already satisfied: python-dateutil>=2.1 in
/usr/local/lib/python3.7/dist-packages (from matplotlib->pyextremes) (2.8.2)
Requirement already satisfied: cycler>=0.10 in /usr/local/lib/python3.7/dist-
packages (from matplotlib->pyextremes) (0.11.0)
Requirement already satisfied: kiwisolver>=1.0.1 in
/usr/local/lib/python3.7/dist-packages (from matplotlib->pyextremes) (1.4.3)
Requirement already satisfied: typing-extensions in
/usr/local/lib/python3.7/dist-packages (from kiwisolver>=1.0.1->matplotlib-
>pyextremes) (4.1.1)
Requirement already satisfied: six>=1.5 in /usr/local/lib/python3.7/dist-
packages (from python-dateutil>=2.1->matplotlib->pyextremes) (1.15.0)
Requirement already satisfied: pytz>=2017.3 in /usr/local/lib/python3.7/dist-
packages (from pandas->pyextremes) (2022.1)
Installing collected packages: emcee, pyextremes
Successfully installed emcee-3.1.2 pyextremes-2.0.0

```

```

aH_serie = pd.DataFrame(H_efect, columns=['Signifiacnt Wave Height - Hs(m)'])
Hs_efect = dir_efect['Signifiacnt Wave Height - Hs(m)'].squeeze()
# Hs_all = Hs_all.squeeze()
Hs_efect.index = pd.to_datetime(Hs_efect.index)

```

Extract the extreme values with Block Maximum Method

```

model = EVA(data=Hs_efect)
model.get_extremes(method="BM",
                  extremes_type='high',
                  block_size="365.2425D",
                  errors='raise')
print(model.extremes.head())
# model.plot_extremes(show_clusters=True)

```

```

Time (years) - From 1979 to 2021
1979-02-19 08:00:00    4.631415
1980-01-03 17:00:00    3.195797
1981-11-10 04:00:00    4.964031
1982-03-21 02:00:00    3.268510
1983-11-29 06:00:00    3.368231
Name: Signifiacnt Wave Height - Hs(m), dtype: float64

```

```

/usr/local/lib/python3.7/dist-packages/pyextremes/eva.py:84: FutureWarning:
Index.is_all_dates is deprecated, will be removed in a future version. check
index.inferred_type instead
  if not data.index.is_all_dates:

```

```

model.plot_extremes()

```

```

(<Figure size 768x480 with 1 Axes>,
 <matplotlib.axes._subplots.AxesSubplot at 0x7f1f7c429990>)

```


Fit the model to data

```
model.fit_model()
summary = model.get_summary(
    return_period=[1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 10, 25, 50, 100, 250, 500, 1000],
    alpha=0.95,
    n_samples=1000,
)
print(summary)
```

```
/usr/local/lib/python3.7/dist-packages/pandas/core/tools/timedeltas.py:142:
FutureWarning: Units 'M', 'Y' and 'y' do not represent unambiguous timedelta
values and will be removed in a future version
    return _coerce_scalar_to_timedelta_type(arg, unit=unit, errors=errors)
```

return period	return value	lower ci	upper ci
1.0	-inf	NaN	NaN
2.0	3.652399	3.485173	3.829818
3.0	3.891876	3.690599	4.109615
4.0	4.045144	3.811647	4.291025
5.0	4.158602	3.898496	4.424637
10.0	4.493753	4.157951	4.836708
25.0	4.917217	4.479715	5.365156
50.0	5.231367	4.719537	5.757084
100.0	5.543197	4.950499	6.154200
250.0	5.953772	5.261539	6.673199
500.0	6.263789	5.492926	7.058161
1000.0	6.573581	5.722983	7.442845

```
/usr/local/lib/python3.7/dist-packages/numpy/lib/function_base.py:4009:
RuntimeWarning: invalid value encountered in subtract
    diff_b_a = subtract(b, a)
```

Estimate and plot the diagnostic

```
model.plot_diagnostic(alpha=0.98)
print(model.plot_diagnostic)
```

```
/usr/local/lib/python3.7/dist-packages/pandas/core/tools/timedeltas.py:142:
FutureWarning: Units 'M', 'Y' and 'y' do not represent unambiguous timedelta
```

```

values and will be removed in a future version
return _coerce_scalar_to_timedelta_type(arg, unit=unit, errors=errors)
/usr/local/lib/python3.7/dist-packages/pandas/core/tools/timedeltas.py:142:
FutureWarning: Units 'M', 'Y' and 'y' do not represent unambiguous timedelta
values and will be removed in a future version
return _coerce_scalar_to_timedelta_type(arg, unit=unit, errors=errors)
/usr/local/lib/python3.7/dist-packages/pandas/core/tools/timedeltas.py:142:
FutureWarning: Units 'M', 'Y' and 'y' do not represent unambiguous timedelta
values and will be removed in a future version
return _coerce_scalar_to_timedelta_type(arg, unit=unit, errors=errors)

```

<bound method EVA.plot_diagnostic

Plot the estimated Return Values

```

model.plot_return_values(
    return_period=np.logspace(0.01, 2, 100),
    return_period_size="365.2425D",
    alpha=0.98,
)
print(model)

```

Univariate Extreme Value Analysis

```

=====
Source Data
-----
Data label: Signifiacnt Wave Height - Hs(      Size:
376,054
                                     m)
Start:          January 1979      End:

```

November 2021

```
=====
                                Extreme Values
-----
Count:                            43      Extraction method:
BM
Type:                              high    Block size:                365
days 05:49:12
=====
                                Model
-----
Model:                             MLE     Distribution:
gumbel_r                           -34.144  AIC:
Log-likelihood:                    72.588
Free parameters:                   loc=3.489  Fixed parameters: All
parameters are free
                                scale=0.447
=====
```



```
extremes = get_extremes(
    ts=Hs_efect,
    method="BM",
    block_size="365.2425D",
)

return_periods = get_return_periods(
    ts=Hs_efect,
    extremes=extremes,
    extremes_method="BM",
    extremes_type="high",
    block_size="365.2425D",
    return_period_size="365.2425D",
    plotting_position="ecdf",
)
```

)

```
return_periods.sort_values("return period", ascending=True).head()
```

```
Signifiacnt Wave Height - Hs(m) \
Time (years) - From 1979 to 2021
1990-12-01 04:00:00                2.817332
2004-01-29 07:00:00                3.013306
2021-01-25 16:00:00                3.095898
2017-09-26 23:00:00                3.139833
2010-11-10 10:00:00                3.187345
```

```
exceedance probability  return period
Time (years) - From 1979 to 2021
1990-12-01 04:00:00                1.000000                1.000000
2004-01-29 07:00:00                0.976744                1.023810
2021-01-25 16:00:00                0.953488                1.048780
2017-09-26 23:00:00                0.930233                1.075000
2010-11-10 10:00:00                0.906977                1.102564
```

Trace plot

```
model = Emcee(
    extremes=extremes,
    distribution="genextreme",
    distribution_kwargs=None,
    n_walkers=100,
    n_samples=500,
    progress=False,
)
```

```
fig, axes = plot_trace(
    trace=model.trace,
    trace_map=model.trace_map,
    burn_in=0,
    labels=[r"Shape,  $\xi$ ", r"Location,  $\mu$ ", r"Scale,  $\sigma$ "],
)
```


Maxim Significant Wave Height

```
maxim = return_periods.loc['2012-02-07 19:00:00']
print(maxim)
```

```
Signifiacnt Wave Height - Hs(m)      5.461863
exceedance probability                0.023256
return period                        43.000000
Name: 2012-02-07 19:00:00, dtype: float64
```

Storm modelated in XBeach

```
oct_xbeach = dir_efect.loc['12-Oct-2016 01:00:00':'12-Oct-2016 21:00:00']
print(oct_xbeach)
```

Time (years) - From 1979 to 2021	Signifiacnt Wave Height - Hs(m) \
12-Oct-2016 01:00:00	2.257677
12-Oct-2016 02:00:00	2.380918
12-Oct-2016 03:00:00	2.495285
12-Oct-2016 04:00:00	2.684901
12-Oct-2016 05:00:00	2.775996
12-Oct-2016 06:00:00	2.876870
12-Oct-2016 07:00:00	3.014781
12-Oct-2016 08:00:00	3.148978
12-Oct-2016 09:00:00	3.235546
12-Oct-2016 10:00:00	3.332436
12-Oct-2016 11:00:00	3.370559
12-Oct-2016 12:00:00	3.340858

12-Oct-2016 13:00:00	3.262621
12-Oct-2016 14:00:00	3.184656
12-Oct-2016 15:00:00	3.097002
12-Oct-2016 16:00:00	2.989788
12-Oct-2016 17:00:00	2.864736
12-Oct-2016 18:00:00	2.764224
12-Oct-2016 19:00:00	2.725558
12-Oct-2016 20:00:00	2.777897
12-Oct-2016 21:00:00	2.916441

Mean wave period - T(s) \

Time (years) - From 1979 to 2021

12-Oct-2016 01:00:00	5.608989
12-Oct-2016 02:00:00	5.751131
12-Oct-2016 03:00:00	5.865363
12-Oct-2016 04:00:00	6.028166
12-Oct-2016 05:00:00	6.135043
12-Oct-2016 06:00:00	6.222448
12-Oct-2016 07:00:00	6.301092
12-Oct-2016 08:00:00	6.397908
12-Oct-2016 09:00:00	6.501648
12-Oct-2016 10:00:00	6.584726
12-Oct-2016 11:00:00	6.657744
12-Oct-2016 12:00:00	6.699391
12-Oct-2016 13:00:00	6.706531
12-Oct-2016 14:00:00	6.685978
12-Oct-2016 15:00:00	6.660340
12-Oct-2016 16:00:00	6.635785
12-Oct-2016 17:00:00	6.598356
12-Oct-2016 18:00:00	6.529232
12-Oct-2016 19:00:00	6.449291
12-Oct-2016 20:00:00	6.386009
12-Oct-2016 21:00:00	6.354422

Mean wave direction - Dr(°) Wave Energy

Time (years) - From 1979 to 2021

12-Oct-2016 01:00:00	110.495436	28.589614
12-Oct-2016 02:00:00	109.435199	32.601845
12-Oct-2016 03:00:00	108.204665	36.520378
12-Oct-2016 04:00:00	106.809327	43.455188
12-Oct-2016 05:00:00	105.705142	47.277573
12-Oct-2016 06:00:00	104.370232	51.499364
12-Oct-2016 07:00:00	102.865025	57.270005
12-Oct-2016 08:00:00	102.178343	63.442070
12-Oct-2016 09:00:00	102.826571	68.064170
12-Oct-2016 10:00:00	104.309804	73.124248
12-Oct-2016 11:00:00	106.177579	75.636400
12-Oct-2016 12:00:00	107.704760	74.774113
12-Oct-2016 13:00:00	108.309041	71.388975
12-Oct-2016 14:00:00	108.281573	67.809402
12-Oct-2016 15:00:00	108.166211	63.882116
12-Oct-2016 16:00:00	108.556246	59.316179
12-Oct-2016 17:00:00	109.358291	54.150823
12-Oct-2016 18:00:00	111.193106	49.889431
12-Oct-2016 19:00:00	114.461712	47.909642
12-Oct-2016 20:00:00	119.043255	49.278996
12-Oct-2016 21:00:00	125.421159	54.048363